

Experimental Studies on Occurrence of Internal Cracks of Blastfurnace Slag Aggregate Concrete

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the mechanism of the failure of the concrete made with air-cooled iron-blast-furnace slag coarse aggregate. Namely, the authors observed the occurrence and growing process of the internal cracks by the microscope, and made clear that the aggregate crack surpassed the bond crack. Furthermore, stress level of the occurrence of bond and aggregate crack were evaluated by J.N.-Goodier's method, and these stress levels were compared with the result of the observation by the microscope.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, it has been hard to obtain natural aggregate, and to use slag aggregate as the coarse aggregate for concrete is of great interest. In relation with this fact, many investigations have been carried out. As the result, since the general characteristics of the strength of slag aggregate concrete indicates the same tendencies as natural aggregate concrete, if the compressive strength of slag aggregate concrete is less than 350 kgf/cm^2 (34.3 MPa), slag aggregate can be substituted sufficiently for natural aggregate. But, considering the singular points of deformation which could be obtained from stress-strain curves (See Fig.1), it is clear that the stress level of the proportional limit of slag aggregate concrete is 10 percent higher than that of plain concrete, and that each stress ratio of the proportional limit, the critical stress and the flow stress are independent of the compressive strength and finally each stress ratio has constant values (See Table 1).

Assuming that the proportional limit is the stress level of the occurrence of the initial crack, and the initial crack is a bond crack between the aggregate and the mortar, the bond crack occurred hardly in case of slag aggregate concrete. Therefore, using the microscope, the authors observed directly the occurrence and growing process of internal cracks and defined them as bond, aggregate and mortar cracks. Furthermore, stress levels of the occurrence of bond and aggregate cracks were evaluated theoretically by J.N. Goodier's method, and the result were compared with the observations obtained by microscope.

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of compressive stress-strain and Poisson's ratio.

Table 1. Comparison of Stress Ratio of Each Singular Points

	Slag Aggregate Concrete (σ_{CB} : 150 ~ 850 kgf/cm ²)	Natural Aggregate Concrete (σ_{CB} : 150 ~ 600 kgf/cm ²)
Stress Ratio of Proportional Limit	Constant Value of 0.55 σ_{CB}	0.46 σ_{CB} at Average
Stress Ratio of Critical Stress	Constant Value of 0.83 σ_{CB}	Function of Compressive Strength
Stress Ratio of Flow Stress	0.96 σ_{CB} at Average	0.95 σ_{CB} at Average

σ_{CB} : Compressive Strength

OBSERVATION OF MICROCRACKS BY MICROSCOPE

Summary of Experiment

High-early-strength Portland cement with a specific gravity of 3.14, crushed and blended sand from Kimitsu in Chiba prefec. with a specific gravity of 2.64 under saturated surface-dry condition, and air-cooled iron-blast-furnace slag aggregate "2505-B" with a specific gravity of 2.40 under absolduted-dry condition were used. The weight of water per unit volume was selected 153 kgf(1.50 kN), determined in accordance with the Japan Society of Civil Engineers recommendation for air-cooled iron-blast-furnace slag concrete. The water cement ratio and sand percentage were 0.45 and 45%, respectively. The slump was adjusted to 7±1 cm by adding non-AE type surperplasticizer. A cubic specimen(10 x 10 x 10 cm) cut from

the specimen for flexural test(10 x 10 x 53 cm) was used to observe microcracks.

The internal microcracks on slag concrete was observed by optical microscope (x 60) at each 24% stress levels corresponding to compressive ultimate strength. The mapmeter was used to measure the length of crack, where grease was used to reduce friction during the loading.

Experimental Results

The cracking map of slag aggregate concrete as the stress increases is shown in Fig.2.

Generally, in case of natural aggregate concrete(1), mortar crack occurred from bond crack between aggregate and mortar. The frequency of the occurrence of aggregate crack was 3% of the length of total cracks, and independent mortar crack occurred rarely

In case of slag aggregate concrete, aggregate crack and bond crack occurred at lower stress level. But the frequency of the occurrence of aggregate crack was twice the frequency of bond crack. Most of the aggregate cracks which formed at lower stress level occurred in porous aggregates, the tendency of which was like the mesh in particles. Examples of aggregate cracks are clear from Phot.1 to Phot. 3. Phot.1 and 2 are examples where crack occurred in failly porous slag aggregate, and Phot.3 is the condition where mortar crack went through in aggregate.

Each frequencies of the occurrence of bond crack, mortar crack and aggregate crack are shown in Fig.3 and 4. Considering these facts, internal cracks of natural aggregate concrete were held by bond and mortar crack, amounted to approximately 97%, while the aggregate crack in case of slag aggregate concrete was approximately 50% of all crack length respectively. Therefore, it is clear that aggregate crack is the main cause of the fracture for slag aggregate concrete. Furthermore, at the stress level of 50%, the summation of bond and mortar cracks length of slag aggregate concrete were only a quarter of natural aggregate concrete. Therefore, in case of slag aggregate concrete, it was considered that stress ratio of proportional limit is 10% higher than that of natural aggregate concrete. This is because the mortar and bond cracks which are the main cause of non-linearity behavior were rarely occurred in case of slag aggregate concrete.

STRESS LEVEL FOR OCCURRENCE OF BOND CRACK

When the elastic modulus of aggregate is a few times higher than that of the matrix(2), considering the fracture of concrete, Hansen determined the stress ratio of radial direction($(\sigma_{rr})_{\theta=90^\circ}$) (See Fig.5) as equation (1).

$$(\sigma_{rr})_{\theta=90^\circ} = -\left(\frac{1-\nu_M}{1+\nu_M} - \frac{5-5\nu_M}{8-10\nu_M}\right)T \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

where (-T): external compressive stress
 ν_M : Poisson's ratio of matrix

Stress level at 24% of σ_{cB} (115 kgf/cm²) Stress level at 48% of σ_{cB} (230 kgf/cm²) Stress level at 72% of σ_{cB} (345 kgf/cm²) Stress level at 100% of σ_{cB} (478 kgf/cm²)

Fig. 2 Cracking map of slag aggregate concrete.

1cm

Phot. 1 Aggregate crack. (Stress level 48%)

Phot. 2 Aggregate crack. (Stress level 72%)

Phot. 3 Aggregate crack. (Stress level 100%)

Fig. 3 Frequency of occurrence of each cracks. (In case of natural aggregate concrete)

Fig. 4 Frequency of occurrence of each cracks. (In case of slag aggregate concrete)

However, Hansen's equation is not reasonable because he considers only Poisson's ratio of the matrix. On the other side, according to Goodier(3), stress of radial direction in the elastic matrix surrounding an elastic inclusion can be determined from Eq.(2).

$$(\sigma_{rr})_{\theta, r=ad}/(-T) \equiv K = \frac{0.5(k-1)}{(7-5\nu_M)k+(8-10\nu_M)} \times \frac{2(1-2\nu_A)(6-5\nu_M)k+(3+19\nu_A-20\nu_M\nu_A)}{2(1-2\nu_A)k+(1+\nu_A)}$$

$$- \frac{\left\{ (1-\nu_M) \frac{1+\nu_A}{1+\nu_M} - \nu_A \right\} - (1-2\nu_A)k}{2(1-2\nu_A)k+(1+\nu_A)} + \frac{0.5(k-1)\{-6+5\nu_M\} + (7-5\nu_M) \cos 2\theta}{(7-5\nu_M)k+(8-10\nu_M)} \dots (2)$$

where $(\sigma_{rr})_{\theta, r=ad}$: stress degree of radial direction defined by Fig.5.
 $(-T)$: external compressive stress.
 E_M, ν_M : elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio of matrix.
 E_A, ν_A : elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio of aggregate.
 k : E_M/E_A

Physical properties of slag aggregate are similar to the mortar matrix(See Table 3). Distributions of stress of σ_{rr} which are shown in Fig.6 are obtained by substituting the values of physical properties of slag aggregate in Eq.2. From these figures, it is clear that the compressive stress does not occur at the pole and that the degree of the tensile stress at the equator line becomes small as the aggregate becomes more porous. Hence, it is considered that bond crack is hard to occur in case of porous aggregate. Assuming that stress of radial direction upon the equator line is equilibrated by bond strength between aggregate and mortar, bond crack will be formed to the length of lc which is shown in Fig.7. Therefore, Eq.(2) can be expressed as Eq.(3).

Fig.5 Coordinates and stress components.

$$(\sigma_{rr})_{\theta, r=ad}/(-T) \equiv K_c = \frac{0.5(k-1)}{(7-5\nu_M)k+(8-10\nu_M)} \times \frac{2(1-2\nu_A)(6-5\nu_M)k+(3+19\nu_A-20\nu_M\nu_A)}{2(1-2\nu_A)k+(1+\nu_A)}$$

$$- \frac{\left\{ (1-\nu_M) \frac{1+\nu_A}{1+\nu_M} - \nu_A \right\} - (1-2\nu_A)k}{2(1-2\nu_A)k+(1+\nu_A)} + \frac{0.5(k-1)\{-6+5\nu_M\} - (7-5\nu_M) \cos(lc/d)}{(7-5\nu_M)k+(8-10\nu_M)} \dots (8)$$

The stress level at the occurrence of bond crack can be obtained by $\cos lc/d > 1$ in Eq.(3), as lc/d which is shown in Eq.(3) approaches zero at the occurrence of bond crack. It was obtained that nominal bond strength of slag particles corresponded to approximately 60% of the tensile strength of mortar matrix(4) by using the briquet mould of A.S.T.M..

Elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio which were shown in Table 3 substituted to Eq.(3). From the result of the calculation, it was obtained that the stress level for the occurrence of microscopic bond crack is $0.19 \sim 0.41$ of σ_{CB} , where σ_{CB} is the compressive strength of concrete. Moreover, the values of 216 tF/cm^2 (2.12 Gpa) and 0.5 were used, as elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio respectively.

The values of K_c in Eq.(3) fluctuates largely with the change of Poisson's ratio of matrix(ν_M). In case where k is $0.51 \sim 0.83$ and ν_M is $0.28 \sim 0.40$ (5), the relationship between the fluctuation of K_c and Poisson's ratio at the proportional limit as well as at the critical stress of slag aggregate concrete which is obtained from 588 specimens are shown in Fig.8. From this figure, it is concluded that the stress level at which bond cracks occurred is approximately 40% higher than the case of Table 3.

Fig.6 Distributions of stress of radial direction.

Fig.7 Length of bond crack(l_c) and central degree(θ_c).

Fig.8 Relationship between K_c and ν_M . ($\nu_p=0.257$, $\nu_{CR}=0.306$)

Table 3 Stress level at occurrence of microscopic bond crack.

	E_A (tf/cm^2)	ν_A	$k = \frac{E_M}{E_A}$	$K = \frac{\sigma_{TR}}{(-T)}$	Natural aggregate		Slag aggregate		
					$-T \frac{0.05}{K} \sigma_{cm}$	$\frac{(-T)}{\sigma_{CB}}$	$-T \frac{0.06}{K} \sigma_{cm}$	$\frac{(-T)}{\sigma_{CB}}$	
Natural aggregate	380	0.20	0.57	0.237	$0.210 \sigma_{cm}$	0.148	—	—	
Slag aggregate	Density slag	420	0.28	0.51	0.225	$0.222 \sigma_{cm}$	0.156	$0.267 \sigma_{cm}$	0.187
	Fairly porous	294	0.37	0.73	0.138	$0.362 \sigma_{cm}$	0.254	$0.435 \sigma_{cm}$	0.304
	Porous slag	260	0.40	0.83	0.102	$0.490 \sigma_{cm}$	0.343	$0.588 \sigma_{cm}$	0.412

σ_{cm} : Compressive strength of mortar

σ_{CB} : Compressive strength of concrete

STRESS LEVEL FOR OCCURRENCE OF AGGREGATE CRACK

According to theoretical consideration of the occurrence of bond crack, the stress level at which microscopic bond crack occur is equal to 18% and 40% of dense and porous slag aggregate respectively. But, in case of slag aggregate concrete, aggregate crack of loading direction has been observed even at 24% of σ_{CB} by optical microscope. Goodier determined stress at the poles of spherical inclusion as Eq.(4).

$$(\sigma_{\theta\theta})_{\theta=0}, r=a/(-T) = \frac{1}{4} \frac{k-1}{(7-5\nu_M)k + (8-10\nu_M)} \times \frac{2(13+25\nu_M)(1-2\nu_A)k + (16+20\nu_M+40\nu_M\nu_A)}{2(1-2\nu_A)k + (1+\nu_A)} + \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{(1-\nu_M)\frac{1+\nu_A}{1+\nu_M} - \nu_A}{2(1-2\nu_A)k + (1+\nu_A)} \right\} - (1-2\nu_A)k \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

where $(\sigma_{\theta\theta})_{\theta=0}, r=a$: stress degree of occurrence at poles of spherical inclusion.

Assuming that tensile crack occurs at the same time in the poles and in the matrix of pole, it can be considered that Poisson's ratios of matrix and inclusion are both 0.5 in plastic area of microscopic crack. Hence, $(\sigma_{\theta\theta})_{\theta=0}$ is

$$(\sigma_{\theta\theta})_{\theta=0}, r=a, \nu_M=\nu_A=0.5/(-T) \equiv K_c^* = 2K_c \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

The relationship between the stress which occurs at the poles and k is shown in Fig.9. In case of $k \leq 1$, the compressive stress works at the poles of aggregate which is assumed to be spherical inclusion, but aggregate crack by tensile deformations is not occurring. Eq.(5) is two times of Eq.(2) which is the stress of radial direction at the poles. The minimum stress at occurrence of aggregate crack(T_c^*) is obtained by the following equation.

$$T_c^* = 0.042\sigma_{CB} / \frac{1}{2} K_c^*$$

where T_c^* : stress level at occurrence of aggregate crack at poles of spherical inclusion.

The relationship between T_c^*/σ_{CB} and k is shown in Fig.10. If the elastic modulus of mortar matrix is 216 tf/cm²(21.2 GPa), since the elastic modulus of porous slag is between 130 and 260 tf/cm²(11.8 and 23.6 GPa), therefore the value of k changes between 0.831 and 1.662. Considering this fact the extent of values of k to form the crack at the pole is $1.112 \leq k \leq 1.662$, and the extent of stress level at the occurrence of the aggregate crack becomes $0.222 \leq T_c^*/\sigma_{CB} \leq 1$.

Fig.9 Relationship between stress at occurrence at pole and k .
($\nu_M = \nu_A = 0.5$)

Fig.10 Stress level at occurrence of tensile aggregate crack at pole of porous slag aggregate.

CONCLUSIONS

In case that natural aggregate concrete make inclusion of matrix, the value of k is less than 1, and aggregate crack does not occur by tensile deformation. But bond crack occurs at comparatively low stress level. In case of artificial light-weight aggregate, the value of k amounts to 1.6 and aggregate crack occurs obviously. When aggregate cracks form, the nominal Poisson's ratio becomes larger and comparing with the occurrence of aggregate crack, bond crack hardly occurs.

On the other side, in case of slag aggregate concrete, since the physical properties of dense slag aggregate resembles natural aggregate, the mechanism of occurrence of internal cracks shows the same tendencies as the case of natural aggregate concrete. But, in case of porous slag aggregate, the frequency of occurrence of aggregate crack is high. If the elastic modulus of matrix is 216 tf/cm² (21.2 GPa), aggregate which has an elastic modulus of less than 194 tf/cm² (19.0 GPa) forms crack at the poles. As the result, crack of slag aggregate which has a comparatively small elastic modulus occurs at 22% of σ_{CB} . This occurrence level corresponds to the result of observation by optical microscope.

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